

*Printed Flexible Patch Antenna for 5G-Subband
Communication with Improved Bandwidth*

By

Dr.Sujata K

**A Final Research Report Submitted for the
fulfilment of the award of
Post Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program in
(Electronics & Communication Engineering)**

**Under Supervision of
Prof. Dr. P.S. Aithal
Vice Chancellor,
Srinivas University,
Karnataka, India**

**College of Engineering & Technology
Srinivas University**

**(A Statutory University under UGC Act, Govt. of
India) Mangaluru- 574 146, Karnataka, India**

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CERTIFICATES

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka-574 146, Mangalore.

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013, Recognized by UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Dr. Sujata K, has completed his Research work at College of Engineering & Technology, City Campus, Pandeshwar, Mangalore as a Research Centre leading to the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program in Electronics & Communication Engineering under the Guidance of Prof. Dr. P. Sreeramana Aithal, Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka for the topic '*Printed Flexible Patch Antenna for 5G-Subband Communication with Improved Bandwidth*' and further I deem the work fit for the submission as a Research report leading to the award of Post-Doctoral Fellow Certificate Program

Place: Karnataka, India

Date: 14/09/2022

Dean
College of Engineering & Technology,
Srinivas University

Research Supervisor's Certificate

This is to certify that the Research Report entitled “Printed Flexible Patch Antenna for 5G-Subband Communication with Improved Bandwidth” submitted to Srinivas University, Karnataka, India by Dr.Sujata K, for the award of Post Doctoral Fellow Certificate in Electronics & Communication Engineering is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Research Report (consist with the Publications) has reached the standard of regulations for the award and it has not been previously formed for the award of any qualifications or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person(s). I recommend that Dr.Sujata K has fulfilled all the requirements according to rules of this University regarding the work embodied in this thesis. I wish him all the success.

Place: Karnataka, India
Date: 14/09/2022

Prof. (Dr.) P. Sreeramana Aithal
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Statutory Declarations

Name of the Candidate: Dr.Sujata K
Title of the Thesis: Printed Flexible Patch Antenna for 5G-Subband
Communicationwith Improved Bandwidth
Certificate: Post Doctoral Research Fellow Program
Name of the Guide: Prof. Dr. P.S. Aithal
Registration Number and Date: 21SUPDR015 of 28/08/2021
Place of Research: College of Engineering &Technology, Srinivas
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Declaration by the Scholar

I, Dr.Sujaka K (Post Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar) hereby declare that the research work presented in this form of Research Report is prepared by me based on my publications (which are never submitted for any qualifications) and all the works have been connected to reach the theme of the topic. The description and narrations found and included are purely original and thus, I declare all such works, result output, framework, policies, suggestions and other Information authentic and original. Moreover, I am responsible for opinions, suggestions and other details found and included in the publications and research report. Hence, once again I declare that the entire work in this research report is original for the award of Post Doctoral Fellow Certificate Scholar of Srinivas University, Karnataka, India

Place: Karnataka, India

Date: 14/09/2022

(Dr.Sujaka K)

DEDICATION

(Beacon of light then, The same today)

To The Lotus feet of ***Lord Shri. Sharnbasveshwar,***
Lingaikya Shri. Poojya. Doddappa Appaji & Shri. Poojya. Sharnbaswappa Appaji,
Sharnbasveshwar Vidya Vardhak Sangha, Kalburagi. Karnataka. India.

Lord Shri. Sharnbasveshwar

Lingaikya Shri. Poojya. Doddappa Appaji

Shri. Poojya Sharnbaswappa Appaji

Also Dedicated to The Lotus feet of my Grandmother *Late. Smt. Shivalingamma*
and my mother *Late. Smt. Tulasabai*

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I am lucky to enjoy their care, patience, deep love and seamless effort by my family members, which gave me courage and stiffness to complete this work in this form and in this stipulated period.

Finally, I would like to express my gratitude and convey my special thanks to those who have helped me directly or indirectly during the entire period of this research work.

- **Dr.Sujaka K**

List of Contributions

The peer-reviewed publications listed below are based on work completed as a part of this thesis.

Publications in the Journals & Conferences

1. Sujata, S. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2021). Inset-fed Multiband Square Patch Antenna on Flexible substrate for Fifth-Generation Wireless Communication. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 5(2), 106-118. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5689664>
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3. Sujata, S. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Simulation Study of Patch Antenna Characteristics loaded with Multislots on Low Cost Dielectric Material. *Proceedings of International conference of Advanced Technology, Sustainability and management 2022 (IATSM-2022)*, Organized by School of engineering & Technology, Sushant University, Gurugram India, 28-29 July 2022. (Proceedings with ISBN in Press)
4. Sujata, S. K., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Study of Dualband Resonance Characteristics of Compact Microstrip Slot Antenna (Submitted to Conference & is published).

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Abstract

Because of its numerous potential advantages, such as being compact, conformal to surfaces, easily integrated with the devices, etc., the antenna has attracted a lot of interest in the wireless industry of the 5G frequency band (home automation mobile communication and industrial applications), over the past ten years. An antenna is often thought of as a conductor that is operable for a particular use in specific application

The patch antenna is one of the most often used solutions for a variety of conceivable antenna designs due to its simplicity in analysis, construction, with less production costs, and favorable radiation properties. It also suffers drawbacks such as low gain, limited bandwidth, surface wave losses, and a large beam width.

The design and analysis of such unique flexible antenna structures are the subject of the study in the current research context and to demonstrate this operation is carried out using the simulation environment. The primary goal of this work is to investigate the performance of broad band antenna models with various structural configurations for applications. Utilizing an EM tool, small and wideband models are designed and analysed. The multi-resonant antenna model design concerns and bandwidth performance improvement strategies with appropriate structures are addressed throughout the entire study. The design method has enhanced the antenna's performance in terms of radiation field, gain, VSWR, minimum return loss, and bandwidth, all of which are important in the 5G domain and also it has mitigated the drawbacks of conventional antenna. In this work, the various antennas are designed for 5G frequency on flexible substrate material and are simulated using EM simulation software for studying the various antenna characteristics in detail as reported in the Chapter four.

Chapter 1

Introduction: Microstrip patch antenna

Chapter 1

Introduction: Microstrip patch antenna

A microstrip antenna in the context of communications is a type of antenna designed on a printed circuit using photolithographic methods (PCB). Array patch components are also used as patches. Patch antennas are made using printed circuit boards, metal traces, or a metal layer that has been etched into the substrate's back side.

The typical types of microstrip antennas are: rectangular, circular, square and elliptical, as shown in fig. 1. The rectangular microstrip antenna in case of open space, the air is utilized as the dielectric substrate. Both the radiation pattern and the impedance bandwidth of a microstrip antenna are impacted by its dielectric loading. With the increase in Q-factor, the corresponding decrease in the antenna bandwidth / the impedance bandwidth is seen.

Fig. 1.Patch Shapes

Generally, the radiation pattern of microstrip patch antenna is broadsided. The microstrip antenna shows less radiation power and bandwidth is narrow. The directivity shown is very less but it can be increased by forming an array using patch antennas. When source power is feed, the electromagnetic waves are produced by the microstrip antenna. The radiation begins from the width side, causing the patch's waves to radiate. The strip end acts as a reflector for the waves generated within the substrate. Due to the discontinuity in the structure, preferences for reflections are possible and antenna radiates only a small portion of the incoming energy that is given. So, it is notable that antenna behaves more like a cavity than a better radiator [4].

The features to design patch are,

1. An extremely narrow conductive region must make up the antenna patch.
2. The ground plane's dimensions must be significantly larger than the patch.
3. functions are enhanced by introducing a thick dielectric substrate with dielectric constant ranging from 2.2 to 12.
4. High directivity is achieved by using microstrip array elements.
5. High beam width.
6. Since they produce a high Q – factor, efficiency is less and bandwidth is also limited. To cover this, the substrate thickness can be increased but after a critical point the thickness will result in an unintended loss of power.

Wireless communications have seen the influence of the use of microstrip patch antenna in prominent applications. To cite an application, the satellite communications antenna radiation patterns, that are generally circularly polarized which in turn can be achieved by a circular or square patch antenna. For example GPS, the placement of GPS makes it expensive and quite small in size. The microstrip antenna has got its application in mobile communications, health care and Radio Frequency Identification. RFID uses frequencies between 30 Hz and 5.8 GHz to function. Numerous communication-related applications, including remote sensing, radio altimeters, environmental instrumentation, command and control systems, feed components in complex antenna, etc., requires microstrip patch antennas. Microwave radiation is thought to be the applicable method in treating malignant tumours by producing hyperthermia and by the use of a patch radiator this can be achieved. [5, 6].

Fig.2. The basic structure of microstrip antenna.

Printed dipoles and annular rings served as the foundation for earlier versions in the design of microstrip radiators intended to induce hyperthermia. The temperature dependent measurement within the human body is performed using two connected microstrip lines with an

alternating spacing. It is surprising to notice that biometric information about the human body are studied using antenna. In order to collect the biometric information and send it to the outside world, they must always be close proximity to the human body. Since attaching the antenna to the human body is not practically possible an antenna fabricated of textile material may be worn without endangering the wearer's health. Conductive cloth materials are used or substrate and copper on it for the patch radiation with the ground plane now they are called textile antenna [7].

Chapter 2

Introduction to 5G

Chapter 2

Introduction to 5G

2.1. 5G technology (fifth generation technology)

The 5G technological standards for broadband cellular network which started rolling in 2019 globally, outwitted the 4G network which was earlier accepted in majority for modern cell phones. The new wireless automation is known to be 5G. The 5G network which is currently being installed across the USA and many other parts of the world, is the replacement of 4G. It is possible to have the internet connectivity between the systems for quick and high-speed data exchange, voice communications to reach out with one another.

In 2018, 5G rollout started and several nations moved as swiftly as they could replace 4G with 5G. The network adopted was widely received by South Korea as the first nation. Few forecasts stated that by the end of 2021, the nations would have not more than 50 million 5G linked subscriptions but an increase of 6.5 million by 2020 will have stake. These figures are anticipated to rise, as more 5G framework is put in place and set the bar high for 5G communication and set the pace for its growth and categorization to advance the whole 5G ecosystem and established the 5G Technology Forum (5GTF) in 2015, collecting the significant partners including Ericsson, Qualcomm, Intel and Samsung. The year 2019 saw the implementation of 5G mobile network service in a few neighbourhoods areas in Chicago and Minneapolis. The first 5G-capable smartphones and 5G networks were available to customers in these selected cities.

In the year 2012, it witnessed the establishment of some ground-breaking work on 5G wireless communications by New York University. ITU-R Working Party (WP 5D) began two topic studies in 2013: (1) Research into upcoming technological advancements for IMT operations and (2) Research into the IMT vision.

In the year 2013, it witnessed a path breaking announcement by Samsung Electronics that they claimed to have established 5G system that transmit data at 1.056 GBPS that covers a distance of 2 KMs. India and Israel joined hands to develop the telecom functioning based on 5G in July 2013. It is said that, South Korea adopted 5G as the first country some time prior to USA, but it disagreed with South Korea's claim by stating that the Country's 5G service was initially applicable to only six South Korean celebrities, but to the astonishing fact, on the day of debut major South Korean telecoms adjoined over 40,000 new users to their 5G networks.

Southeast Asia's first country to put out a 5G technology was Philippines and it was done on June 2019. Before launching 5G nationwide in the first part of the year 2020, AT & T offered 5G service to customers and its companies in December 2019 [1-3].

A simple definition of 5G is the fifth-generation mobile network. a new technology that incorporates every valuable aspect from earlier generations, such as 1G, 2G, 3G, and 4G, in order to create a better system that may provide users more advantages than the present 4G and LTE technologies.

The goal is to give consumers a bandwidth over a gigabit per second and the latency need, which is to be within one millisecond. There are some basic requirements that a technology must meet in order to classify as 5G:

- 1–10 Gbps connectivity to field endpoints.
- A round-trip delay from end to end of 1 millisecond.
- 1,000x bandwidth per square foot.
- 10 to 100 times as many linked devices.
- A 99.99% uptime guarantee.
- Total coverage
- A 90% decrease in network energy use.
- Low power, machine-type gadgets can have batteries that last up to ten years.

The researchers claim that, the 5G technology can handle speeds of up to 10 Gbps and a large variety of radio channels; it will provide continuous and reliable coverage, or “wider area mobility in genuine sense”. The 5G infrastructure is highly complex, and many terminals and network parts are often upgraded with technically superior performance. Similarly, consumers and distributors may simply embrace value-added services by implementing this advanced technology.

For 4G, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing is a better choice to get good performance. Higher spectrum efficiency, which can be processed and controlled at all levels suitable with modern mobile phones, is something it can offer. So, it can perform better while operating with higher data rate covering wide bandwidths.

The development of 5G technology in tandem with smart cities will increase demand for mobile network functionality and performance. Since, it provides then services such as, interactive multimedia, audio and video Internet, and other broadband services, which are more effective and enticing. Unbelievably fast internet connection speeds ensure that there is always capacity to fulfil client demand. It will carry out all the tasks you want without any speed or data rate degradation, regardless of how many customers are connected at once [8, 9].

2.2. 5G Antenna

Globally, people who use mobile, desire to have the dependable resource like higher data speed in 5G. With the 5G discovery, it is claimed that, the users will be proficient to download a high definition data in less than a second using this 5G high-speed service. Additionally, these networks will accelerate the spread of other cutting-edge simulations like the internet of things, virtual reality and automatic vehicles.

It was planned to introduce the initial 5G networks in the early 2020s and was implemented even before the year 2020. The telecommunication authorities were strict on one thing: 5G must be able to task much more traffic at much faster rates than the existed networks.

Engineers developed a number of novel technologies to carry out the above stated task. Thus, they found that users experienced peak downloading rates of 20 gigabits and data delivery within a millisecond of latency.

It is essential to go through the five technologies like millimeter waves, massive multiple output multiple input (MIMO), beamforming, full duplex and small cell network in order to grasp how 5G will differ from the 4G network.

Millimeter waves: The challenge faced by the non-wired network is the consumption of more data by the gadgets than it was supposed to be, yet it is still being jammed onto the radio-frequency spectrum band of the identical bands. Because of the shorter bandwidth, which will result in the slow functioning and more disconnections, this may be achieved by connecting mobile users with a nearby base station using millimetre waves, which is an entirely innovative approach.

Massive MIMO: Wireless systems known as massive MIMO systems use two or more transmitters and receivers to broadcast and receive large amounts of data concurrently. A signal propagation scheme is used in 4G/LTE which is known as multiple output multiple input (MIMO). Since, 5G base stations may accommodate up to 100 ports, large number of antennas can fit on a single array thus increasing the capacity of mobile networks.

Beam forming: It is traffic signalling system for cellular base station as shown in fig. 3. that finds the most efficient route to a particular user to determine the most effective data distribution path to a specific user while minimizing interference for surrounding customers. There are various approaches for 5G networks to deploy it, by considering the circumstance and technology. One such approach is beam forming.

Fig. 3. Beam forming technique

Full duplex and small cell network: To optimize 5G signal transmission a different technology called full duplex is used. The existing technology need data messages to take turns coming and going, or in other words it will use different paths for sending and receiving. Introducing 5G will change all that. Silicon transistors are used as high-speed switches to control these signals which allows for true duplex on frequency band.

Small cell network approach: Small cell networks are built on the idea of avoiding an impediment rather than overcoming it. It is not easy for the millimeter waves to travel through obstacles. During such situation, this network permits the signal to go past the obstacle [10, 11].

The three 5G use cases of 5G are:

- **Massive machine-to-machine communication:** The concept of Internet of Things that links billions of devices at a scale that has never been accomplished till. This has the potential to completely transform current industrial uses, including manufacturing, agriculture and business communications.
- **Ultra reliable low latency communication:** low latency communications are needed for automatic driving, also in robot automations, vehicle to vehicle connections and also for safe transportation. The low latency also helps in widening the remote medical care that is a telemedicine service.
- **Enhanced mobile broadband:** High internet speeds and more volume are offered globally by the modified mobile broadband. The new applications will include fixed wireless connection for houses, broadcast apps without broadcasting vans, and it will also have the significant exposure for individuals in terms of services.

2.3 5G network

The 5G works will ensure a constant connection; the majority of operators will first combine 5G networks with current 4G networks. The two essential components of a mobile network are the radio access network and the core network.

Radio access network: The radio access network is a crucial component of wireless communication systems. Through a radio link, this network is utilised to connect individual devices to various network nodes. From the first generation (1G) until the fifth generation (5G), it has been a part of the communication system.

Core network: The mobile exchange and data network known as the Core network is responsible for overseeing all mobile phone, data, and internet facilities. To boost response times and provide a better user experience while interacting with the internet and cloud-based services, the "core network" is being redesigned for 5G with scattered servers. Many of the complex characteristics of 5G, like network work function virtualization and network slicing for different users and services, will be managed by the core network.

Network slicing: A method of separating network for industry, business and for any other applications.

Network function virtualization: A software can perform network operations that uses firewall and encryption [10].

The block diagrams as shown in fig.4, exemplify the main electronic designs that have been seen, from modem to antenna, and the parts that are enabling 5G devices.

Fig.4. Diagram of 1st Generation 5G

Through fig. 4, it is fairly evident that the initial designs are of an additive nature. The parts of it are, single-mode 5G modem, a 5G RF transceiver, and a 5G RFFE with a single band. SDRAM and PMICs make up as the 5G modem's supporting components. DRAM semiconductor memory in the form of synchronous dynamic random-access memory operates more quickly in terms of speed than traditional DRAM. Power management integrated circuit manages power on electronic devices like mobile phones. RFFE (RF Front End) provide a pathway between the antenna and the modem through a transceiver unit [12].

2.4 Advantages of 5G

- High speed transmission: With the help of a 5G network, a transmission speed of 15/20 Gbps can be obtained. Thus, with this high-speed transmission, we can make maximum use of the cloud without depending on the internal storage of the device. The computing tasks can also be performed on the cloud simultaneously.
- Low Latency: The time taken by a device to send a message and receive its response is known as latency. The 5G provides low latency which is approximately ten times less than 4G.
- Greater no of connected devices: With the help of 5G it is possible to connect large number of devices. When connected to 5G network, the gadget will have an immediate entry to the internet and share information with one another device. This increased number of connected gadgets will enable autonomous vehicle and smart cities.
- Network slicing: This can be the way of generating numerous distinctive logical and virtualized networks about the same multi-domain framework. It helps in the utilization of network resources and service flexibility to a great extent [13, 14].
-

2.5 Disadvantages of 5G

- High Initial Cost: For the development of the framework in modification of the 5G structure, the cost for which might be very high initially. A large sum is also needed to guarantee the better connectivity. With the concept of network sharing, cellular operators will try to reduce the cost.
- Effect on Device Battery: When the devices are connected to 5G, the battery drains out faster. The cell phones which are connected to 5G are experiencing thermal heating as reported by the users. The technology of the battery must be modern in order to get a full usage with a single charge.

- Upload and Download Speeds: In 5G network, it is experiencing to note that the download speed is up to 1.9Gbps. Whereas the uploading speed of 5G is very less as compared to the downloading speed, which hardly goes beyond 100 Mbps. But when compared to 4G network, the 5G network provides high downloading and uploading speed [13,14].

2.6 Frequency Allocation for 5G Worldwide and in India

The number of 5G users will strengthen every day because of the better speed and more bandwidth offered by 5G. The first band, often known as the sub-6 GHz or sub-7 GHz band, has a frequency range of 410 MHz to 7125 MHz. This band is used by LTE and LTE-Advanced systems. One drawback is that the majority of frequencies are still in use, making it impossible to ensure a large, ordered frequency range.

Table 1: 5G frequency band

Areas	5G Frequency Band
Europe	3400 – 3800 MHz (awarding trial licenses)
China	3300 – 3600 MHz (ongoing trial)
China	4400 – 4500 MHz
China	4800 – 4990 MHz
Japan	3600 – 4200 MHz
Japan	4400 – 4900 MHz
Korea	3400 – 3700 MHz
USA	3100 – 3500 MHz
USA	3700 – 4200 MHz

The second band is between the range 30GHz to 100GHz. 3GPP defines the millimeter band between the frequencies from 24250 MHz to 52600 MHz. Because of the fact that the band being rarely used, it provides wideband [15, 16].the table 1 shows the 5G band of frequencies and table 2 shows the frequency allocation in world.

Table 2: Uplink and downlink frequency allocation

Band	Uplink Frequency (MHz)	Downlink Frequency (MHz)	3GPP band no.	Duplexing Scheme
700 MHz	703 – 748 MHz (35 MHz has been earmarked for Access services)	758 – 803MHz	28	FDD
800 MHz	824 – 844 MHz	869 – 889 MHz	5	FDD
900 MHz	890 – 915 MHz	935 – 960 MHz	8	FDD
1800 MHz	1710 – 1785 MHz (55 MHz has been earmarked for Access services)	1805 – 1880 MHz	3	FDD
2100 MHz	1920 – 1980 MHz	2110 – 2170 MHz	1	FDD
2300 MHz	2300 – 2400 MHz		40	TDD
2500 MHz	2500 – 2690 MHz		41	TDD
3300-3600 MHz	3300-3600 MHz (25 MHz spectrum (3400 MHz – 3425 MHz) is identified for ISROs use in Indian Regional Navigation Satellite System (IRNSS))		Not yet auctioned but has recommended: i. TDD Duplexing scheme ii. Barring the locations where ISRO is using the 25 MHz of spectrum, the entire is to 3300 - 3600 MHz should be access for services.	

This band provides high speed, huge capacity data communication. The high air signal attenuation will be the drawback in this band. The two methods adopted are:

1. Non-standalone (NSA)
2. Standalone (SA)

The Non-Standalone method, utilizes an amalgamation of a New Radio (NR) technology. Likewise, the standalone method, utilizes a distinctive 5G NR technology where in, this data is dispatched and accepted by getting hold of the control among the base station and mobile terminal.

Fig.5. Picture showing NSA and SA mode

In 5G, the communication frequency band and operation modes are unique. Different countries are moving on with ways to employ the NSA mode in the millimeter wave band after considering a number of frequency bands and the operation mode in its prior 5G service.

In USA, fixed broadband circuits may get deployed whereas densely populated areas like Japan and South Korea are aiming for increased data transmission [17- 19].

2.7 Limitations of 5G Antenna

At this time, all significant telecoms providers are implementing 5G cellular technology. But, there are both merits and demerits for this 5G communications. They are listed below:

- Proximity: Although 5G mobile networks are regularly adding new towers and communication, the proximity will still be a problem. To get good 5G connectivity, it is required to stay close to the 5G framework. So, the good network has to be available in crowded cities.
- Spectrum and Bandwidth: Service suppliers are sharing the radio frequency between the 5G and 4G for proper utilization of spectrum and bandwidth. The carriers are expanding their allocated spectrum for making availability for high-speed 5G. By using network slicing, the 5G carriers make use of their network to a great extent. It can also help in handling more uses and transferring more data simultaneously.

- Rural and Distant areas: The companies mainly concentrated on crowded city areas than the distant village areas for 5G communication. But the providers have started talking about a secured 5G possibility to fasten the network by home Wi-Fi in this distant isolated area. Although there are many 5G applications in industries like farming, mining and in these areas, the providers may not observe it is feasible to install the network. To become it feasible a huge number of consumers are needed in those areas [16].
- Security: It is the main trouble for the providers, users and business. It is believed that 5G gives improved security. The service providers have to understand these updated security systems of 5G, but for the business that to create a network assistance above all 5G networks, knowing these security techniques will be essential for the services [20, 21].

2.8 Applications of 5G

- Utilizing the power of IoT:
- Immersive Gaming and Virtual Reality:
- Unlock Artificial Intelligence (AI)
- Industrial Applications
- Health Care
- Logistics

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Chapter 3

Literature survey

Chapter 3

Literature survey

The literature survey is carried out to study the techniques, trends, methods used for antenna development as explained below:

Ashraf Badawi [1] proposed an effective method for analyzing aperture-coupled microstrip antennas. This work formulates the method of integral equations for mixed electromagnetic currents and combines it with the method of moments. The boundary conditions are ensured based on the precision of the method adopted in this study. The paper also deals with computational efficiency which was found to be satisfactory in terms of antenna parameter results.

Suidong Yang et al., [2], has discussed about GaAs monolithic microwave integrated circuit sequential rotated active antenna for 4.4 GHz oscillator. The designs issues has been discussed in the study. Spatial power combination and circular polarization characteristics have been studied and in-phase oscillator entrainment is shown. The findings demonstrate the circular polarisation properties of the structured antenna array.

On a wide-band planar antenna, *Shi-Chang Gao et al.* [3] reviewed theoretical and experimental findings. By creating an H-shaped aperture paired with stacked square patches, the bandwidth is determined. Calculating the impedance bandwidth shows it to be 21.7%. This is shown in the return loss curves. Good cross-polarization levels of less than -23 dB are seen in the E and H planes. It can be seen that the effective front-to-back ratio of the antenna radiation pattern is 22 dB.

This article by *C.H. Cheng et al.* [4] examined a novel aperture-coupled patch antenna in which the patch is surrounded by a conductor ground and the edges of the dielectric substrate are lined with conductor walls. When the antenna was examined, it was shown to have an average gain of roughly 7.4 dBi and a bandwidth of 28% (for $|S_{11}|$ -10 dB) at 10 GHz. A good radiation pattern is observed, in this study.

F. Javier González et al., [5], has given the idea of detector that consisted of Fresnel zone plate coupled antenna of detection of 2D array. This antenna is a simple element square–spiral antenna coupled nickel coupled bolometers. The observed 2D pattern is directional in nature.

F.J. Gonzalez et al., researched square-spiral antenna-coupled microbolometers made of gold and chrome that are etched on a silicon-nitride membrane in their study [6] in the year 2005. This element is used in commercial infrared-imaging systems for mechanical stability. For mechanical stability, this component is utilized in commercial infrared imaging systems. When the manufactured devices are taken at ambient pressure and vacuum, the result yields D^* values of 3×10^6 cm Hz/W and 1.7×10^7 cm Hz/W, respectively. The values of more than 1×10^8 cm $\sqrt{\text{Hz/W}}$ for D^* can be found with the use of vanadium-oxide. The antenna coupled dictation has been studied on silicon-nitride membrane.

The properties of aperture coupled microstrip antennas on magnetised ferrite substrates were investigated by *Germán León et al.*, [7]. The full-wave analysis of a magnetised ferrite-layered medium in an aperture-coupled microstrip was done. The patch antennas sub-sectional basis operations are used in this work. Ferrite substrates powered by single microstrip lines radiate in both circular and linear polarisation as a result of the mathematical conclusions. The matching frequency band of the antennas can be changed for a polarised condition by adjusting the strength of the inclining magnetic field. Also, the polarisation state is changed from circular to linear by altering the strength and direction of the inclining magnetic field.

The design of single feed aperture coupled microstrip antennas for WLAN was studied by *Rashid A. Saeed et al.*, [8]. This research presents a theoretical analysis and simulation of high-speed input impedance behaviour that can support 80 MHz-bandwidth 2.4GHz WLAN applications. A patch is centred in the slot for optimal coupling. Even if a slit is cut along the H plane's direction, there is essentially no impact. For maximal coupling, the coupling level is kept lower with the resonance patch's E-plane slit. In relation to the slot's centre, the feed line is positioned at an angle. In order to reduce the coupling, feed line position at different locations with respect to the patch is also shown. By, theoretical investigation that be conducted in order the result shows better matching of 2.4 GHz with better VSWR.

The design and development of a photonic band gap (PBG) shared-aperture dual-band aperture fed patch antenna were discussed by *N C. Karmakar et al.*, in 2005 [9]. The suggested antenna is superior to the reference antenna, according to a comparison analysis. More than 30 dB of isolation and a 1 dB gain were also obtained between the receiving and transmitting terminals.

The comparison of the simulated and measured characteristics of active and passive aperture coupled microstrip antenna design was studied by *M. K. A. Rahim et al.*, in their publication [10]. Here, an aperture linked feeding method is employed. This paper describes the designs, simulation, fabrication and measurement of active and passive rectangular patch with non-contacting feeding technique. The active and passive aperture linked microstrip antenna has a bandwidth of 0.025 GHz, or 1.04%.

In 2006, *P. K. Day et al.*, [11], studied that planar antennas for millimetre and submillimetre wavelengths might be connected with a microwave kinetic inductance detector (MKID). The variations in Kinetic inductance are determined using microwave high-Q thin film superconducting resonators. Microstrip lines were used to connect the manufactured microwave kinetic inductance detector to the submillimetre slot array antennas, and power was ducted from a thermal radiation source.

N. Ghassemi et al., [12], treated the ultrawideband applications of the dual stacked rectangular aperture coupled microstrip antenna. The paper deals with the frequency of the patch's changes with respect to slots, length and position, and later the substrate position. At the resonant frequencies of 4.1 GHz and 4.5 GHz, the impedance bandwidth is 36.7 GHz, and the gain bandwidth is 8 dB.

A scattering estimation strategy for antenna characterization is studied by *Pekka Pursula et al.*, [13]. The modulation is accomplished when a known RF power is sent from the antenna to the oscillator circuit. This makes it easier to estimate an antenna's radiation pattern and bandwidth. A precision of 9% is measured for the antenna aperture. With the reactive load, measurements of the bandwidth and radiation pattern are thought to have good precision. The PIFA core frequency was found to be 5 MHz and a dipole antenna was detected around 869 MHz.

An aperture coupled patch antenna (ACPA) made completely of wearable textile material was introduced by *Carla Hertleer et al.*, [14]. In case of ACPA, microstrip feed line is used instead of rigid coaxial field. The outcome of this paper is exceptionally effective, completely adaptable. The antenna operates at 2.45 GHz ISM band with bandwidth of 145 MHz.

The design of a dual stacked microstrip antenna at 9.5 to 16 GHz frequency range was proposed by *N. Ghassemi et al.*, [15]. According to studies, the new structural design, improves

the antenna's impedance bandwidth to 44%. The thickness of the antenna is reduced by a factor of 0.14. Additionally, the antenna's gain bandwidth expands by 5.1 GHz (40%).

A unique aperture coupled microstrip antenna with an asymmetric U-shaped feeder and two rectangular slots on the ground was developed by *N. Ghassemi et al.*, [16]. The maximum gain bandwidth (7 dB and higher) of the antenna is 6.6 GHz (47%). According to the results, the VSWR of the antenna is less than 2 at 10.5–22 GHz. The simulation and test findings successfully match each other.

F. Venneri et al., [17] conducts a thorough investigation, by reducing the spacing between the components on the aperture linked reflection array layout and calculating the bandwidth are carried out. The operating frequency range calculated by numerically and validated with the gain pattern. It showed a strong wideband operation with array of medium aperture size and limited unit cell size. The gain pattern modified for the 20 GHz reflected array $D= 12.6\lambda_0$ and $34\lambda_0$.

On the central station antenna of the Local Multipoint Distribution System (LMDS), a patch-based molding beam reflectarray that is aperture-coupled to a delay line has been demonstrated by *Eduardo Carrasco et al.*, [18]. It operates in the 10.10–10.70 GHz region. The antenna has a cosecant pattern in elevation and spans a 60 ° azimuth sector. The development and testing of a V-polarized breadboard in an anechoic chamber demonstrates a good correlation between the theoretical and observed radiation patterns. With a better radiation pattern, the sector's minimum gain was 18 dB.

A parasitically connected T-shaped microstrip patch antenna investigated by *D. Neog, K., and S. Patnaik*, *S* is described in the publication [19]. The T-shaped microstrip patch substrate allows for dual-band resonant frequencies on a thin substrate. A broad impedance is indicated by the 3dB bandwidth for two resonant frequencies. The radiation patterns and impedance plot are generated to demonstrate the dual-band of frequencies. The antenna has two unique frequencies at 19.73 GHz and 24.05 GHz, according to the measured data, which are consistent with the estimated values.

In the year 2003 *Seok H. Choi et al.*, [20], has studied about an ultrawide band for UWB applications. This antenna operates between the frequencies 3.2 GHz and 12 GHz. The measured group delay shows a value less than 0.5ns of variation. The radiation pattern frequencies 3, 5 and 7 GHz are found out and the antenna gain between the range 3-10 GHz were discussed.

S Bhunia et al., [21], give an idea of reduced size small dual and multi-frequency micro strip antennas. The two rectangular slots are cut to yield this new structure. A reduction in patch size up to 85% over a conventional rectangular patch antenna. The adjustment of the field position of a conventional rectangular antenna results in obtaining dual frequency operation in an effective manner.

In this paper, *Yusnita Rahayu et al.*, [22], introduced a printed ultra-wide band antenna with couple slot. To broaden the band width of this antenna a coupled L and U slots are etched on patch. The patch antenna's current distribution influences how the slots are designed. With a -10 dB return loss for UWB appliances, the anticipated return loss covers the UWB spectrum from 2.5 GHz to 10.1 GHz.

Hamsakutty Vettikalladi et al., [23], investigated and presented a structured, high-gain super substrate aperture-coupled patch antenna array at 60 GHz. The gain and radiation pattern of the antenna will be significantly impacted by the addition of a certain size super substrate. At 60 GHz, a 2x2 super straight antenna array has a maximum measured gain of 16 dBi and a 63% efficiency, which is 4 dB greater than a conventional 2x2 array. The observed VSWR bandwidth at 2: 1 is 6.8%. Additionally, a 4x4 super substrate antenna array's maximum recorded gain is 19.7 dBi, with a corresponding efficiency of 51%. Over the entire frequency range, the radiation pattern is broadside with negligible back radiation.

The aperture paired microstrip patch antenna's optimization was shown by *M. Dogan et al.*, in their study [24]. The feeding structure used for the patch element that radiates will differentiate this antenna from other microstrip antennas. The radiation patch is coupled with the input signal by the opening that is on the ground surface of the microstrip feedline. These types of antennas are made up of many layers that are stacked with many design variables which in turn influence the working of the antenna. High gains attained and derived for minimum VSWR much less than two.

Rajesh Kumar Vishwakarma and Sanjay Tiwari [25], has demonstrated aperture coupled microstrip antenna. This research compares a single patch antenna to a microstrip aperture coupled antenna based on the air gap dielectric. An aperture coupled microstrip antenna has a relatively high input impedance and band width. According to the article, the ratio of resonance frequency varies between 2.1 GHz and 1.1 GHz when the air space between the antennas increases. The measured return loss is -14 dB with impedance bandwidth of 35%.

In the year 2011, *Arindam Deb et al.*, [26], utilizes the differential evolution (DE) algorithm to design an aperture coupled microstrip antenna. The fitness function for DE is defined by the microstrip transmission line model. Using binary coded genetic algorithms and particle swarm optimization (PSO), the calculated outcomes of DE are contrasted. The dielectric constant of the substrate's design is 2.32 and its height is 1.57 mm.

Zarreen Aijaz and S.C. Shrivastava [27], has looked at, on how an aperture-coupled microstrip antenna's form affects coupling. Coupling aperture shape will significantly affects the strength and coupling between the feed line and patch. The impedance loci point near to the center and the measurement of resonant frequencies versus stub length are carried out.

Tanveer Kour Raina et al., [28], described an aperture coupled microstrip patch antenna. The suggested antenna is made of two substrates with thicknesses of 0.762 mm and 0.508 mm, and it is intended to operate at a frequency of 10 GHz. Parametric study is conducted to understand the impacts of stub length, slot length and dielectric constant on return loss. The antenna is having -37 dB of return loss with bandwidth of 200 MHz.

A cavity-backed aperture- linked microstrip patch antenna array was proposed by *C. Hua et al.*, in [29]. It comprises of a feed network and two elliptical patch antennas with connected apertures. The metallic cavity is used behind the antenna array to decrease back radiation. The outcome showed that the suggested antenna has better -3dB for E-plane and H-plane beamwidths at 55.80 and 77.60 GHz respectively. The pattern also achieves a deep null of -32.4 dB. From 34.2 GHz to 36.6 GHz, the return losses for both sum and difference ports are less than -10 dB. The bandwidth versus return loss is plotted, and it is determined to be 6.8%. The isolation between the sum and differences is better than 38 dB within this bandwidth.

Bikramjit Goswami and Kandarpa Kumar Sarma [30] looked into how to maximise the power of an electrically powered antenna array's reconfigurable aperture. This paper put forward that, the antenna array with electrically adjustable aperture area can use the neural networks ANN1 and ANN2. The idea of adaptive power optimization for antenna arrays generated from ANN results in power savings and effective performance that utilized for wireless communication fields. The calculated and estimated impedance for different aperture area values are varying low to compare.

Parismita A. Kashyap and Kandarpa Kumar Sarma [31], studied and discussed the techniques for reducing the fading impact in various multi antenna configuration. For BPSK, DPSK, and QAM modulations, Rayleigh flat and Rayleigh frequency selective fading is the proposed approach. The bandwidth of transmitted signal is 10 KHz in aperture microstrip.

R. Akhbar et al., [32], studied the fabrication, optimization and the study on various substrate thickness of aperture coupled microstrip antenna. The design is built at 2.4 GHz center frequency. Board substrate thicknesses is changing from 1.27 mm to 2.54 mm. The study of physical parameters is done by computer simulation technology (CST). Reflection attenuation (S11), gain, VSWR and frequency results for various substrate thicknesses are evaluated. The antenna parameter is calculated and the results are acquired using a vector network analyzer (VNA). The directivity found to be 5.596 dBi and simulated bandwidth is about 3.96 % and for measurement, the bandwidth is 21.99%.

Milind Thomas et al., [33], described idea of feeding technique utilizing electromagnetically coupled microstrip T junction. The stimulated bandwidth is 175 MHz and 170 MHz. The 6 dB: gain bandwidth is 211 MHz with 84% efficiency. The measured band width is 170 MHz at 5.16 GHz frequency

A work on modified microstrip aperture linked patch antenna with Sierpinski fractal geometry was published by *Hao Jiang et al.*, [34]. With proper working, the impact of parasitic patches and coupling slots is examined. The developed antenna operates in the frequency ranges of 956 MHz to 968 MHz, 3.654 GHz to 3.78 GHz, and 8.81 GHz to 9.28 GHz, with a peak gain of 4.64 dBi, 8.46 dBi, or 7.85 dBi for each band, respectively. In terms of radiation properties, the findings are better.

Wide band aperture coupled parasitic patch antenna was described by *Arvind Shekhar Joshi and Dharendra Mathur* [35]. The proposed antenna can be designed to function 24.12 GHz, ISM band. By addition of gap coupled parasitic elements, the bandwidth greater than 5 GHz is studied with better radiation pattern.

The suggested antenna coupled splitting resonator for biosensing applications is described by *H. Torun et al. in* [36]. The sensor is made up of a dielectric substrate and a metallic ring with a slit. Above the substrate there's an integrated monopole antenna and metallic plate width is fixed behind the substrate. This paper shows that, the resonant frequency is

reduced by dielectric loading. Biosensor is used from probing interaction between FGF-2 and Heparin. The sensitivity of the instrument is found out to be 3.7 MHz. The device's resonance frequency is 2.12 GHz.

A.H. Majeed et al. developed a portable dielectric resonator antenna for wide band uses in this study [37]. At the intersection of the rectangular patch coupling are the two cylindrical dielectric resonators, which are arranged asymmetrically. With a frequency range of 9.62 to 12.9 GHz and an 8 dBi gain, the impedance bandwidth is 29%.

Muhammed Waqas et al., [38], studied about a different Double Negative (DNG) material that enhanced the function of Microstrip Patch Antenna. MPA superstrate is now DNG that diminishes the surface waves and thus reduces the losses. The directivity, gain and radiation efficiency are the results obtained. 5.45 dB to 6.237 dB and 6.87 to 7.18 increase in directivity band gain is observed. Radiation efficiency also improved from 72% to 80.42 %.

In this article *Lisha Zhang et al.*, [39], considered the design of an aperture coupled based lens array for a tightly packed 60 GHz LEPA system. A layer of 250 micrometre low-loss microwave laminate wrapped in two layers of 18 m thick copper makes up the lens, along with a 34x34 array of antenna, filter, and antenna components. A broad bandwidth between 55 and 65 GHz is attained with a return loss of less than 10 dB. The isolation was also wanted to be better.

A miniaturised inverted U-slot aperture linked wideband microstrip patch antenna was proposed by *Amandeep Singh and Surinder Singh* [40]. The suggested antenna's properties include wideband behaviour, acceptable return loss, VSWR, gain, compact size, and low complexity. The outcomes show that the antenna has improved impedance matching and return loss in the frequency range of 11.08 GHz to 13.25 GHz. The black dotted plot exhibits 790 MHz to 2170 MHz absolute bandwidth.

Ishu Mishra et al., studied the analysis and potential uses for dual-frequency patch antennas in the publication [41]. In order to create the microstrip patch antenna, HFSS software is used. The return loss, VSWR, and Z parameter have all been used to analyse the antenna's performance. The results show that a gain of about 18.5 dBi and bandwidth of more than 10% are produced.

The aperture coupled microstrip patch antenna work was reported by *Niaz Muhammed* [42] to introduce a high gain cavity resonant antenna. FSS superstrate has got high

reflection at $|\Gamma| > 0.9$. To find the resonant angle of the antenna, Ray tracing method was used. Cavity resonant antenna (CRA) analysis was performed using design variables. A high gain of 13.97 dBi was obtained, was used as simulation tool.

A theoretical analysis of a rectangular patch antenna with parasitic components and a split ring resonator was presented by *Ashish Sing et al.* in 2017 [43]. By adjusting the aforementioned parts' length and width, the antenna demonstrated dual band functionality. It is determined that 0.9 GHz and 1.8 GHz are the lower and higher resonant frequencies, respectively. The outcome displays a 2.0 frequency ratio and a 1.8 dBi maximum gain.

In the year 2017, *Debashish Pal* [44], proposed on an aperture coupled printed antenna for broadband radio services. The frequency of the antenna is operated at 2.56 GHz. To obtain better cross polarization and to make an isolation between patch and the feed circuit, the antenna uses the aperture coupled technique. The structured study is done using a soft designer. Low profile, lightweight properties of the antenna help to unify with radio frequency circuits. The antenna coupled of 140 MHz bandwidth having fractional bandwidth of 5.5 % and 2.56 GHz of resonant frequency is with a peak gain of 3.08 dB centre frequency.

The design of the C-band aperture linked microstrip patch array was examined by *C.N. Sujatha et al.*, in the publication [45]. The paper reports the purpose of designing aperture coupling is to obtain wide frequency bandwidths and low back radiation. In this case, the increased bandwidth is obtained by coupling the microstrip antennas on one board from the microstrip line feeds on another board through an opening on the ground surface. The theoretical gain is 16.7 dB and the practical gain is 13.7 dB. The result shows that the HPBW is 80° theoretically and 74° practically for single element and for 4×4 planar array the HPWB is 24.6° theoretically and 25° practically.

The 5G MIMO antenna elements in mobile terminals which was studied by *Jari Holopaine et al.*, [46]. Various antenna configurations are related with respect to the ergodic capacity. The aperture frequency range is of 1-6 GHz and the mutual coupling better than -12 dB in the lossless case.

In this paper [47], *Muhammed Ikram et al.*, introduce an integrated design consisting of a (MIMO) antenna framework for 4th generation applications and a planar associated array (PCA) for 5th generation applications. The designed coupled of printed for element integrated band MIMO antenna system with slot band PCA. For the MIMO antenna structure and the PCA, the

predicted gain and efficiency values at the centre frequency are respectively 3.4 dBi and 74% and 8 dBi and 80%.

The far-field characterization of 5G antenna was studied by Benoit Derat et al., [48]. Dynamic range problems and high expense were the main drawbacks of far-field 5G antenna. The customarily involved equation for the far field distance targets restricting the impinging field face curvature. Spherical wave expansion theory defines two novels far-field distance. Findings show that very short distance than the accepted distance is utilized to figure out the precise far field value.

AK. Hamid and W Obaid [49] published the Hexa-band MIMO CPW bow-tie aperture antenna that has six frequency bands operating at 2.4, 4.4, 6.1, 8.5, 10.25 and 12.8 GHz. The construction of the same comprises of four loaded bow-tie hexa-band antenna in which every particle is headed with every 6 metallic strips. Additionally, MIMO bowtie antennas exhibit incredibly low mutual coupling across all operating frequencies for the specific loaded metallic strip width.

For the next 5G communications technology, *D Imran et al.*, [50] presented a microstrip patch antenna with a bandwidth of 1.94 GHz and 2 GHz. Here microstrip-line feeding method is utilized. For mobile data applications, an array with four components and a 4mm spacing is described. A microstrip antenna exhibited a gain of 6.9 dB for 58 GHz and 7.4 dB for 54 GHz. Additionally, when a four-element linear array produces a gain of 12.2 dB for 38.6 GHz, 11.6 dB for 47.7 GHz and 12.1 dB for 5 GHz when used.

A 5G communication design for the mm wave new multiband microstrip patch antenna was studied by *Zeesham Lodro et al.*, in [51]. The 5G millimetre wave antenna based on microstrip technology is affordable, low profile, high gain, and efficient. Realized gain of the 5G microstrip antenna is adequate at 5 dBi and 6 dBi the radiated and efficiency is 65% at 37 GHz and 75% at 64 GHz is obtained. It is simple to incorporate into small gadgets and is employed in 5G communication.

P Jothilakshmi et.al., [52] gave a description of an aperture connected patch antenna for S-Band communication. The stacked patches present in the proposed antenna removes the coupling loss. Construction and execution of three substrate layers aperture coupled antenna is shown. The different performance variable like return loss, gain band width and radiation pattern are re-enacted and estimated.

Using MATLAB software, *Damaraju Sri Sai Satyanarayana et al.*, [53] presented an aperture coupled patch antenna design. To understand the influence on antenna functioning, the aperture coupled patch antenna's microstrip feedline, boards, ground plane slots, and patch dimensions have been changed by using a dielectric board distanced by a ground plane with radiation conductors which removes electrical connections between feeds. By selecting the correct combination of slot feed shapes will give the best impedance bandwidth with modified radiation patterns. The radiation plot is designed by taking 2.45 GHz operating frequency that gives efficiency 99.6%.

In the article, *Faza Syahirah Mohd Noor et al.*, [54] presented a dual band linear polarised antenna with harmonic rejection that operates at frequencies of 2.45 GHz and 5.00 GHz. In addition to the 50 Ω feeder an improved inverted π -slot etching patch is set up at the bottom of stack antenna to improve antenna directivity at operating frequencies 2.45 GHz and 5.00 GHz. The harmonic elimination feature is carried out by introducing U grooves and asymmetrical stubs in the transmission feedline to diminish undesired harmonic signal from 6.00 GHz to 10.00 GHz. A harmonic suppression up to -4dB is achieved with a better RL of -18.87 dB at 2.45 GHz and -19.54 dB at 5.00 GHz..

The design of the aperture coupled microstrip patch antenna employed for air surveillance radars was studied by *D. Anand Kumar and R.G. Sangeetha* [55]. The design and implementation of the antenna are looked at in terms of return loss gain, efficiency, directivity, and power factors. The antenna discussed here achieves a gain 5 dB, the directivity accounts to 4.5 dB with an efficiency of 30 % and above 15 % impedance greater than an inset feed line. Moreover, with return loss of about – 40 dB is acquired relative to the - 19 dB of the inset feed line patch antenna with the help of suitable impedance matching.

For small and integrated wireless devices, a common aperture 5G antenna system is suggested by *Muhammed Ikram et al.*, [56]. The 3.6 GHz dipole antenna is powered by an improved balun consisting of a microstrip line and a tapered slot. The radiation Pattern beams out of the mm-wave arrays and the tapered slot antenna may scan 120° area with a realization of 8 dB of beam.

Olutola Jonah presented the 5G Sub-6 GHz MIMO antenna design and examined the features of the antenna in the year 2020 [57]. Parameters like gain, directivity, efficiency, envelope correlation co-efficient and the radiation patterns are discussed.

Bing Liu et al., in 2021 [58], designed the possibility to create two brand-new low ϵ_r gallates, MgGa_2O_4 using a common solid-state reaction technique. With rising sintering temperatures, the SEM pictures show consistently improved microstructures. The designed antenna demonstrates a good radiation coefficient in the required sub- 6 GHz range, with a return loss of -19.94 dB and a VSWR of 1.22 dB at 4.84 GHz. Simulated overall efficiency for the proposed antenna is 1.38 dB.

The structure of highly scalable MIMO B5G mm wave smart skins and large area reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for IoT and smart city applications, as well as phased arrays for 5G / B5G mm wave smart skins and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, are described in the paper [59] by *Xuanke He et al.* Instead of employing arrays of various sizes to provide coverage for users of various capacities. This architecture may easily scale up to very large arrays by simply adding additional tiles and increasing the feeding network on the mounting tiling layer. A proof-of-concept 32 element antenna array based on 29GHz 22 times was created. A beam steering range of +/-30 is shown.

The design of a multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antenna array for a 5G millimetre wave communication system is discussed in this study by *Jalalkhan et al.*, [60]. The suggested MIMO setup combines two antenna arrays. The 37 GHz frequency spectrum intended for 5G millimetre wave communication applications is covered by the proposed antenna array. The gain of the MIMO antenna element is 6.84 dB, which is improved to 12.8 dB by employing a four-component design. Within the designated operational frequency, the proposed MIMO antenna array is said to have a radiation effectiveness of more than 85%. Center frequency for ports 1 and 2 is 38.04 GHz, respectively, while the bandwidth for ports 1 and 2 is 37.29 to 38.64 GHz.

By studying the survey papers, it has been seen that, the research has to be reported and studied by employing different techniques, by the low dielectric constant based material which are flexible and suitable for embedding in wireless application. Some of the techniques involves use of novel slots, slits placed towards the not radiating and radiating edges which can make the antenna work for 5G band respectively with improvement in bandwidth. The next chapter deals with the design and simulation of the various antennas suitable for 5G applications, which are simulated using CST EM simulation software (trial/student version).

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Chapter 4

Publication in the domain area

Inset-fed Multiband Square Patch Antenna on Flexible substrate for Fifth-Generation Wireless Communication

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Over a decade, the antenna has sparked considerable interest in the 5G frequency band in the wireless domain (covering industrial applications, home automation and mobile communication) because of its numerous advantages like compact, conformal to surfaces, easily integrated with the devices, etc. In general, an Antenna can be defined as a conductor which is exposed to space operable for a specific application. The purpose of the study is to design the Slotted patch antenna for 5G applications on a flexible dielectric substrate material which makes the antenna compact in its design aspect.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Initially, the antenna design is carried out using the theoretical framework based on the available equations. The microwave studio software - Computer Simulation Technology (CST) is used to create and model the different antennas.

Findings/Result: Based on the simulated models, the slotted patch antenna design 5 has 2 bands namely: 3.25 GHz, the return loss is -17.47 dB, and 5.89GHz, the return loss is -21.37dB. Whereas design 6 has 4 resonant bands measured at 2.04 GHz, the return loss (RL) is -11.68 dB, at 5.80GHz, the RL is -22.36 dB, at 7.14 GHz, the RL is -28.71 dB and at 8.83 GHz, the RL is -13.36 dB. The maximum bandwidth achieved for slotted patch antenna design 5 is 5% and the maximum bandwidth achieved for slotted patch antenna design 6 is 8%. Whereas the design of Multi slotted patch antenna flexible substrate design 7 and design 8 has the maximum achieved bandwidth of 10 %.

Originality/Value: The design of slotted patch and multi slotted patch antenna using inset feed method on a flexible substrate for 5G frequency band.

Paper Type: Design based Research Analysis.

Keywords: Multiband antenna, 5th generation wireless communication, Inset-feed method, Electromagnetic wave propagation, Return loss of antenna, Slotted Patch Antenna, Flexible substrate.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The microstrip antenna in 5G frequency band of wireless arena (industrial applications, home automation and mobile communication) has been intensively used because of its numerous advantages like compact, conformal to surfaces, easily integrated with the devices etc. In general, Antenna can be defined as a conductor which exposed to space operable for specific application. Because of its ease of analysis and construction, less production costs and appealing radiation properties, the patch antenna is one of the most commonly utilized solution for several possible antenna configurations. It also suffers few drawbacks such as low gain, limited bandwidth, surface wave losses and a large beam width.

2. RELATED WORKS :

N. Mohamed Sobidha Banu, et al, (2015), focussed the inset feed approach, the square microstrip patch antenna with a frequency of 2.6GHz that is suited for S-band applications is designed. The researcher concentrated on the magnitude and antenna performance. The antenna is intended for S-band communication at 2.6GHz, with a radiation pattern that covers a large angle of beam and a strong gain. The recommended antenna's resonance frequency is good, as is the return loss, VSWR [1]. Zain Ul

Abedin and Zahid Ullah (2017) investigated the high-bandwidth, high-gain microstrip patch antenna for UWB and other wireless communications. The main aim is to obtain a large bandwidth, by using FR4 dielectric material of 1.6mm thick having ϵ_r of 4.4. As the consequence, the antenna's bandwidth ranged from 2.33 GHz to 12.4 GHz, with 90% efficiency in radiation for the UWB region. The antenna's coverage range is from 3.1GHz to 10.6GHz, which is a wide band range. It also encompasses the scope of a local area network as well as the scope of satellite communication for both uplink and downlink [2]. In the paper, P Saleem Akram et al, (2018), the microstrip line feed with slotted patch was carried out. The design was done using HFSS software. The placement of a slot at the ground enhances the bandwidth. In comparison to previous models, the design consists of 10 iterations at the three edges of the UWB with high gain. It intends to be in the Ultra-wide band range (3.1GHz - 10.6GHz) for WiMAX, WLAN 802.11, and LTE 42/43 [3]. Nikita M. Tarpara et.al., (2018), designed the slotted microstrip patch for 5G application. By loading some slots within the radiating patch, the lower resonance was seen in this study because of surface-current paths meandering on patch, consequently the bandwidth increases. This frequency varies slowly for different slot width in comparison with antenna without slot. It helps the bandwidth as well as the gain to increase in accordance with the slot width [4]. 5G mm-Wave patch was investigated by M.D. Madhan and D. Subitha (2019). Due to several microstrip antenna disadvantages, the researchers of this work have considered aspects on how to enhance them. By using Detected Ground Structure (DGS) technique, the efficiency, bandwidth, the gain are enhanced [5]. Muhammad Afiq Abdul Aziz et al designed a microstrip patch antenna for 5G at several frequencies over 20GHz (2019). This antenna was designed on RT duroid Substrate whose ϵ_r is 2.2. The designed antenna has a fractional bandwidth, gain, and directivity of more than 10.2 percent, 2.159dB, and 2.562dB, respectively [6]. Naser Ojaroudi Parchin, et al, (2020) proposed a loss-profile dual-band MIMO patch antenna array for 4G/LTE and 5G wireless communication with better isolation. The feeding mechanism consists of two coaxial-fed patch antennas with U-shaped slots that provide dual-band operation in the 2.6/3.6GHz 4G/5G bands. As the consequence the isolation is enhanced by about 13dB and 10dB at the operation frequencies with the parasitic structure [7]. Rezaul Azim et al (2020) shows a multi-slotted patch for long term evolution (LTE) and 5G. It uses three slots to enhance the capacitive effect. The antenna gives omnidirectional radiation pattern, great gain and efficiency, to give the suggested antenna a chance to be used for WiFi, WLAN, LTE, 5G, etc [8]. The work reported by Kalsouabe Zoukalne, et al, (2020) about the design of microstrip patch antenna array for 5G which resonate at 3.6GHz. It was designed on Rogers RO4350 (tm) substrate, having a thickness of 3.54mm and $\epsilon_r=3.66$, it contains three slots, in which, two are put in the radiating elements and one on the power line. The proposed antenna provides a gain of 9dBi and a bandwidth of 200MHz [9]. M. M. Hasan Mahfuz et al, (2021), demonstrate the use of a ring shape resonator (RSR) on the ground to create a UWB patch antenna with a 5G lower band notch. The VSWR, return loss, 2-D radiation pattern, surface current, radiation efficiency, and gain all show that it is an excellent 5G solution [10]. Mohammad Alibakhshikenari and colleagues (2021) investigated a wide-band sub-6GHz self-grounding Bow-tie antenna with a novel feeding method for 5G communication systems. This antenna covers 3.35 to 4.4 GHz. It is composed of two petal shaped metal structure. Electromagnetic coupling is used as the method of feeding the petals, with the principle of an open circuit [11] as a result of all of these designs. The current study presents the design of slotted and multi slotted patch design on flexible dielectric substrate material designed for 6GHz suitable for 5G applications.

3. OBJECTIVES :

The paper deals with the antenna design on flexible dielectric substrate and extending with the slotted patch antenna designs based on the available methods as noted in literature review within the design simulation constraints. The adopted method in the designs will be studied to meet the below objectives:

- (1) To theoretically design the patch antenna that can be validated with the simulated designs for 6GHz frequency.
- (2) To design the slotted and multi slotted patch antenna with inset fed excitation method.
- (3) To develop computer simulated antenna design suitable for 5G wireless applications.
- (4) To determine return loss, bandwidth and radiation characteristics of the patch antennas.
- (5) To perform simulation iterations of the designed antenna on the CST microwave studio and to obtain the desired resonance.

4. METHODOLOGY :

This paper consists of patch antenna designed using a theoretical framework based on the available equations [12] that are available. The antennas are fed with Inset feeding method and the different antennas are designed and tested using the Computer Simulation Technology microwave studio software.

5. DESIGN AND RESULTS :

The various designs are considered in this present study and initially it starts with the simple flexible patch antenna, followed by Slotted Patch Antenna-Design 5 and 6 and Multi Slotted Patch Antenna-Design 7 and 8.

5.1 Design and Results of Simple Flexible Patch Antenna:

Figure 1 shows the design of a slotted flexible patch antenna constructed on a Kepton polyimide substrate material having dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r) of 3.4, the equations used to calculate the dimensions as given in [12] and the dimensions of simple patch antenna are, Patch length (L) is 1.66 cm, Patch width (W) is 1.66cm, both Ground length (Sl) and Ground width (Sw) is 1.68cm. The flexible substrate thickness (HS) is 0.0125 cm and its copper thickness (HP) is 0.0035cm. The flexible patch is fed with inset-fed excitation method and its dimensions are; width of feed (wf) is 0.1 cm and the inset length (Fi) is 0.44 cm. The calculated dimensions are the functions of the operating wavelength as per the chosen design frequency 6GHz which is acceptable for 5G wireless band applications. The design of simple square patch antenna selected is designed at 6GHz frequency and is as shown in figure 1. EM-CST (SV) computer software is used for antenna design. The simulated antenna has an RL of -11.52dB and operated at 5.35 GHz. The simulated resonance is quite close in agreement with chosen design frequency and hence validates the theoretical design.

Fig. 1: Simple patch antenna (on flexible substrate)

Fig. 2: Graph of S₁₁ for Simple square patch antenna (on flexible substrate)

As per the above figure 2, it is also observed that, the antenna is resonating at two different bands for simple square patch antenna with RL of -11.52dB at 5.35 GHz and a RL of -12.03dB at 9.67 GHz, which is acceptable for a normal operation in the frequency band. Hence, this type of single antenna (Simple patch antenna (on flexible substrate)) can be used for both transmission and reception for application in 5G band. The maximum bandwidth achieved for this is 3 %. The surface current distribution on simple flexible square patch antenna is shown in Figure 3. It is clearly seen that the radiation happens along the width side of the patch. The maximum current concentration is from feed

portion to the edges of the patch.

Fig. 3: Current distribution for Simple patch antenna (Flexible substrate)

Fig. 4: a) 2D and b) 3D patterns for simple square flexible patch antenna

Figure 4 shows the 2D and 3D radiation patterns working at 6 GHz, having a major lobe magnitude of roughly 6.15 dB. The main lobe direction is at 0°, the antenna radiates up to an angular width of 94.3 degrees, and with minor side lobes of -5.5dB. From the figure it is clear that, this antenna radiates in broadsided nature.

5.2 Design and Results of Slotted Patch Antenna-Design 5 and 6:

Figure 5.a and 5.b represent the design of slotted-patch antenna with different type of slots shapes. The both design 5(a) and 5(b) have the same dimensions as that of simple patch antenna except the fact that they have some slots with different shapes and sizes. These dimensions are functions of wavelength factor like half wavelength and fractional wavelength with respect to the actual considered wavelength.

Fig. 5: a) Slotted Patch Design 5, b) Slotted Patch Design 6 (on flexible Kepton polyimide substrate)

The dimensions and position of the slots for Slotted Patch Design 5 on flexible Kepton polyimide substrate are given as:

For First slot:		
Slot Width	$-W/2+0.2$	$W/2-0.35$
Slot Length	$-L/2-0.9$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP
Second slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.62$	$wf/2+0.62$
Slot Length	$wf/2+0.65$	$wf/2+0.0.6$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP

The dimensions and position of the slots for Slotted Patch Design 6 on Flexible Kepton polyimide substrate are given as below:

First slot:		
Slot Width	$-W/2+0.2$	$W/2-0.35$
Slot Length	$-L/2-0.9$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP
Second slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.62$	$wf/2+0.62$
Slot Length	$wf/2+0.65$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP
Third Slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.61$	$wf/2+0.61$
Slot Length	$-wf/2+0.63$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP
Fourth Slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2+0.15$	$wf/2-0.14$
Slot Length	$L/2-1.5$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot Thickness	HS	HS+HP

Fig. 6: Graph of S11 Slotted Patch Antenna for Design 5 and Design 6 on flexible Kepton polyimide substrate

Figure 6 represents the graph of S-parameter (RL or S_{11}) of Slotted Patch Antenna: Design 5 and Design 6 on Flexible Kepton polyimide substrate. Both the designs have obtained a good return loss, comparatively. The Slotted Patch Antenna for design 6 has better S_{11} output characteristic in the form of multiband nature because it represents more bands as compared to the design 5. The maximum bandwidth achieved for Slotted Patch Antenna- Design 5 is 5% and the maximum bandwidth achieved

for Slotted Patch Antenna- Design 6 is 8%. The design 5 has 2 bands namely: the first resonance is at 3.25 GHz with the RL of -17.47 dB, and the second resonance is at 5.89GHz with the RL of -21.37dB. Whereas, the design 6 has 4 resonant bands measured at 2.04 GHz, the RL -11.68 dB, at 5.80 GHz, the RL of -22.36 dB, at 7.14 GHz, the RL of -28.71 dB and at 8.83 GHz, the RL of -13.36 dB. The obtained bandwidths are enhanced due to the addition of single and double inverted C type slots in both the designs due to which the current elongation on the surface of the patch increases which make the antenna resonate at multiband frequencies as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7: a) Current distribution for Slotted Patch Design 5, b) Current distribution for Slotted Patch Design 6 (on Flexible Kepton polyimide substrate)

Figure 7 (a) and 7 (b) represent the surface current distribution on the patch, designed on flexible substrate. Both figures show the currents are disturbed accordingly and distributed on all patch area and on slot. The current becomes high in the edges of the slots, which creates multi resonance.

(b)

Fig. 8: a) 2D Radiation pattern for Slotted Patch Antenna. a) Design 5 and b) for Design 6 (flexible substrate)

Figure 8(a) and 8(b) represent the 2D polar radiation pattern for Slotted Patch Antenna design 5 and design 6 fabricated on Kepton polyimide flexible substrate. For the design 5, at resonance 6 GHz, the main lobe direction is of 1.0 degrees, the main lobe magnitude is of 5.74dB, the angular width is of 94.0 degrees and a side lobe level of -7.9dB, whereas, in the design 6, operating at the same operating frequency, the main lobe magnitude is 4.07dB at main lobe direction of 40.0 degrees.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9: a) 3D patterns. a) slotted patch design 5 and b) slotted patch design 6 (flexible substrate)

Figure 9(a) and 9(b) represent the 3D Radiation pattern for both design 5 and design 6 for Slotted Patch Antenna on Kepton polyimide flexible substrate. The arrows indicate the direction in which the power is radiated. As it is clearly visible, the radiations are broadsided in nature.

5.3 Design and Results of Multi Slotted Patch Antenna-Design 5 and 6:

The next type of slotted antenna design involves the etching of plus shape slot and the design of without plus shape slot with wider rectangular slots. The figure 10. (a) and 10. (b) represent the design of multi slotted patch antenna with different slots and shapes. The design as shown in figure 10. (a) and 10. (b) have the same dimensions as that of simple patch antenna except the fact that they have some more slots with different shapes and sizes as a function of operating wavelength.

Fig. 10: a) Multi Slotted Patch Design 7, b) Multi Slotted Patch Design 8 (on Flexible kepton polyimide substrate)

The dimensions and position of the slots for Multi Slotted Patch design 7 on flexible Kepton polyimide substrate are given as:

First slot:		
Slot Width	$-W/2+0.2$	$W/2-0.35$
Slot Length	$-L/2-0.9$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Second slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.62$	$wf/2+0.62$
Slot Length	$wf/2+0.65$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Third slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.61$	$wf/2+0.61$
Slot Length	$wf/2+0.63$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Fourth slot:		
Slot Width	$-W/2+0.15$	$W/2-1.4$
Slot Length	$L/2-1.5$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Fifth slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.45$	$wf/2-0.28$
Slot Length	$-sl/2+dl+0.09$	$sl/2-dl-L+fi$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Sixth slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.35$	$wf/2+0.35$
Slot Length	$-wf/2+0.03$	$wf/2-0.03$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP

The dimensions and position of the slots for Multi Slotted Patch design 8 on Flexible Kepton polyimide substrate are given as below:

First slot:		
Slot Width	$-W/2+0.2$	$W/2-0.25$
Slot Length	$-L/2-0.9$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Second slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.62$	$wf/2+0.62$

Slot Length	$wf/2+0.65$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Third Slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2-0.61$	$wf/2+0.61$
Slot Length	$-wf/2+0.63$	$wf/2+0.6$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP
Fourth Slot:		
Slot Width	$-wf/2+0.15$	$wf/2-0.14$
Slot Length	$L/2-1.5$	$L/2-0.19$
Slot thickness	HS	HS+HP

Fig. 11: Graph of S11 for both design 7 and 8 (Multi slotted antenna for flexible substrate)

Figure 11 represents the graph of S-parameter (S_{11}) of Multi Slotted Patch Antenna for design 7 and design 7 on same flexible Kepton polyimide material. Both the designs have obtained a better return loss, comparatively. The Multi Slotted Patch Antenna for design 7 has better S_{11} output characteristic and is in the form of triple band nature because it represents more bands as compared to the design 8. The maximum bandwidth achieved for Multi Slotted Patch Antenna- design 7 is 9% and the maximum bandwidth achieved for Multi Slotted Patch Antenna- design 8 is 10%. The design 7 comprises three main bands: the first is at 1.98 GHz and has a RL of -13.61 dB, the second resonance is attained at 6.169 GHz and has a RL of -22.1 dB, and the third resonance is at 8.13 GHz and has a RL of -24.0 dB. The Multi Slotted Patch Antenna for design 8 contains two simulated resonant bands, with RL of -21.4 dB at 5.8 GHz and RL of -25.7 dB at 7.2 GHz. The achieved bandwidths and minimum return loss are enhanced due to the addition of wider rectangular slot with plus shape slots in the center of patch slots in both the designs due to which the current elongation on the surface patch increases making it to have triple band characteristics as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 12 (a) and 12 (b) represent the surface current distribution on the patch, designed on Multi Slotted Patch flexible substrate. Both figures show the currents are disturbed accordingly and distributed on all patch area and on slot the current becomes high in the edges of the slots, which creates dual and triple resonance for 5G wireless communication applications.

Figure 13 (a) and 13 (b) represent the 2D radiation polar plot for multi-slotted flexible substrate. For the design 7, at resonance 6 GHz, the main lobe direction is of 5.0 degrees, the main lobe magnitude is of 5.84dB, the angular width is of 80.3 degrees and a minor side lobe level of -4.8dB, whereas, in the design 8, operating at the same operating frequency, the main lobe magnitude is 5.5dB at main lobe direction of 179 degrees, having angular width of 70.9 degrees and minor side lobe level of -8.3dB. Figures 14(a) and 14(b) illustrate the 3D radiation patterns for Multi Slotted Patch Antennas on flexible dielectric substrates with minimal side lobe levels for designs 7 and 8. The arrows in the patterns indicate the direction in which the power is radiated. As it is clearly visible, the radiations are broadsided in nature with less cross polar levels.

Fig. 12: a) Current distribution for Multi Slotted Patch Design 7, b) Current distribution for Multi Slotted Patch Design 8 (on Flexible kepton polyimide substrate)

Fig. 13: a) 2D Radiation pattern for Multi-Slotted Patch Antenna. a) Design 7 and b) for Design 8 (flexible substrate)

Fig. 14: a) 3D Radiation pattern for Multi Slotted Patch Antenna. a) Design 7 and b) for Design 8 (on flexible substrate)

6. CONCLUSION :

The work reported in this paper has five designs of simple patch, two designs of slotted and multi slotted patch antenna on flexible substrate. The slotted patch antenna design 5 has 2 bands namely: 3.25 GHz, the return loss is of -17.47 dB, and 5.89GHz, the return loss is of -21.37dB. Whereas, the design 6 has 4 resonant bands measured at 2.04GHz, the RL is -11.68 dB, at 5.80 GHz, the RL is -22.36 dB, at 7.14

GHz, the RL is -28.71 dB and at 8.83 GHz, the RL is -13.36 dB. The maximum bandwidth achieved is slotted patch antenna Design 5 is 5% and the maximum bandwidth achieved for slotted patch antenna Design 6 is 8%. Whereas the design of Multi slotted patch antenna flexible substrate Design 7 and Design 8 has the maximum bandwidth achieved is 10 %. The multi slotted designs has also attained multiple resonance suitable for 5G applications with better return loss having good radiation characteristics.

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Slit Loaded Compact Shaped Patch Antenna for 5GHz Wireless Application

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study and design of flexible patch antenna with different inset gap width fabricated on RT Duriod 5880 substrate for fifth generation wireless application is presented in this article. The patch is composed of slits along the length and width separated by copper ground plane on backside and is directly fed by inset feed. The antennas resonated at multiband characteristics with better return loss (RL) suitable for fifth generation wireless and other indoor communication based applications. Radiation patterns are nearly broadsided with a heart like shape for resonant band of frequency.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The antenna is designed using a theoretical framework based on known equations as in literature. To construct and model the various antennas, the Computer Simulation Technology (CST) free student edition is employed.

Findings/Result: By the proposed simulated models, the slit based patch antenna design 1 has achieved dual band characteristics with bands namely: at $fr_1 = 4.5$ GHz (with return loss up to -30 dB) having bandwidth 1.5% and $fr_2 = 10.5$ GHz (with return loss up to -26 dB) having bandwidth of 2.2%. Whereas, the design 2 has again dual resonances at lower and higher frequency bands with the reduced return loss up to -23 dB at $fr_1 = 4.5$ GHz having bandwidth 1.5% and $fr_2 = 12.5$ GHz with return loss up to -17 dB having bandwidth of 14%. Hence, the antenna design 2 has achieved the maximum bandwidth of 14% suitable for wireless applications, RADAR, Fixed-satellite services.

Originality/Value: The design of slits cut on patch by varying inset feed width gap on flexible substrate for 5G frequency band is investigated.

Paper Type: Original Research Contribution.

Keywords: Wireless system, Multiband, RT Duriod, Patch antenna, Slits

1. INTRODUCTION :

Thin, lightweight, high gain simple antennas are key factors in ensuring reliability, portability, mobility in today's wireless communication systems. So, Microstrip antennas meet all these criteria's to be suitable for wireless applications. Huque, M. T. I. et al., (2011), focussed on the microstrip antenna's features which include conformability to the mounting surface, relative ease of assembly, least weight, minimum cost for implementation and a thin projection of copper layer on the surface of the dielectric material. This antenna takes full advantages/benefits from the concept of PCB technology. The use of microstrip antennas are found in satellite communication applications, radar and medical applications based wireless communication applications [1]. The main drawbacks of the microstrip antenna include constricted bandwidth nearly to 1%, low gain and high Q factor which make the antenna less efficient for 5G based applications. Robert J. Mailloux, et.al., (1981), discussed about the goal of microstrip antenna design is to maximise the desirable bandwidth while lowering the VSWR [2] by decreasing the mismatch between the input and load. This paper also reported the different feed methods so as to improve the characteristics of microstrip antenna. ChengChi Hu et al., (2000) reported an X-band 4x1 aperture coupled, series fed, electronically operable microstrip leak wave antenna (LWA) array design with dual beam radiation patterns and two-dimensional (2D) beam

scanning capabilities. The proposed antenna array is suitable for wireless communications and radar systems [3]. K. Gi-Cho, et al. (2003) investigated the Ku-band, a linearly polarised microstrip array may achieve excellent efficiency by having correct impedance matching across the array and properly exploiting the corporate and series feeds by microstrip transmission lines. To achieve a somewhat broad bandwidth, the cavity-backed microstrip patch is utilised. In the azimuth orientation, the auto-tracking Ku-band antenna has created with a very low profile for car rooftop mounting, as well as a reduced production cost [4]. Abbaspour Tamijani, A., & Sarabandi, K. (2003) reviewed the design and manufacturing aspects of an affordable flat-beam steerable-array antenna with a simple design, stating that by way of grouping the elements of an array into a number of sub-arrays that partially overlap the array, and the use of a single-phase phase shifter for each sub-array will result in array size reduction and cost-of- production also [5]. By the use of moment method technique, the zero surface impedance and scattering characteristics of a patch antenna are investigated by Boufrioua A. and Benghalia A. (2006) [6]. The integral equation of the current is derived using the electric field boundary condition. Radar scattering cross-section (RCS) of the microstrip antenna as well as the effect of surface resistance and uniaxial substrate were studied. K. C. Lo and Y. Hwang. (1997), studied that compact version the patch antennas can be obtained (i.e., smaller in size) by using high permittivity materials [7] to be used in 5G applications. J. M. Rathod (2010), developed a 750 MHz centre frequency microstrip rectangular patch antenna on FR4 PCB dielectrics. The antenna employed a probe feed approach to feed power via a semi rigid coaxial cable with a 50-ohm impedance, with a completely copper plated PCB serving as the patch's ground plane [8]. The measure the radiation pattern, resonant frequency, bandwidth of an imperfectly conductive annular microstrip printed on a uniaxial anisotropic substrate, a full-wave approach was used [9] by Barkat O. and Benghalia A. (2009). The Galerkin's approach was also used to solve E-field integral equation. High efficiency and gain at millimeter wavelengths are the characteristics exhibited by microstrip superconductors. The results are compared to previously published data and are determined to be very similar [9]. Choon Sae L. and Kuo-Hua. T. (2005) explored hybrid antennas for broadband wireless devices with constrained antenna size. The prototype antenna has a bandwidth of 23.5 % and a steady radiation pattern with little cross-polarization. [10]. Islam, M. F. et al. (2010), presented a coaxially-fed single-layer small dual band (C- and X-band) microstrip patch antenna capable of having dual-polarized radiation for use in airborne synthetic aperture radar (SAR) systems. With a VSWR of less than 2, the constructed antenna reaches impedance bandwidths of 154 MHz ($f_0 = 6.83$ GHz) and 209 MHz ($f_0 = 9.73$ GHz) [11].

In the current work, the design of flexible patch antenna with different inset gap width fabricated on RT duriod 5880 substrates for fifth generation wireless application is carried out. The proposed design is able to function in at least more than two other frequency ranges satisfactorily, with wide bandwidth and better return loss. Details of the modelled antennas are described.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE PAPER :

This work aimed to design antennas on RT Duriod 5880 material with slits cut on the patch to achieve the desired resonance suitable for fifth generation applications in lower frequency. In addition to the paper as listed in the literature review, so the designs are carried out within simulation constraints. The methodology applied in the designs will be studied to meet the following objectives:

- (1) To study antenna characteristics like RL, 2D and 3D Radiation plots, SWR and current distribution.
- (2) Slit-patch antenna compact design with inset excitation method.
- (3) Modelling of antenna designs suitable for 5G wireless applications using computer simulation software (student edition).
- (4) For antenna design in low frequency 5 GHz with varying inset width of the copper patch.
- (5) To obtain multiple resonance with better SWR.

3. ANTENNA DESIGN PROCEDURE :

Antenna performance and its accuracy is always proportional to its size The resonant frequency, RL, SWR and factors are impacted by the chosen dimension of microstrip antenna. Firstly, convention design with inset-fed patch is considered and then slits are cut of this patch surface keeping its length and width unchanged. All prototypes are fed by a 50 Ω conventional connector in the CST software (student version) and are implemented on RT duriod 5880 substrate dielectric material.

To obtain efficient performance of patch, initially, patch (length \times width) has to be mathematically calculated by equation 1&2 [12].

$$W = \frac{c}{2f_r} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2}\right)} \quad \text{-----} \quad (1)$$

The antenna patch length equation is written as,

$$L = \frac{c}{2f_r \sqrt{\epsilon_r}} - 2\Delta l \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

At chosen frequency of operation, 5 GHz, the calculation yielded, the patch length and width ($A \times B$) of the patch is (19.98 \times 23.70 mm). The length and width of inset fed is optimized to get the better results as depicted in fig.1. The patch is designed on RT duriod 5880 substrate material of thickness $h = 0.5\text{mm}$ and permittivity $\epsilon_r = 2.2$. The slit dimensions are considered as a factor of free space wavelength (λ_o) as compared with conventional antenna intended design frequency i.e., 5 GHz.

Fig.1: Geometry of Patch -top view. a) Conventional design, b) Design 1, & c) Design 2

The slit lengths and widths of design 1 and 2 are same (C) are 1 mm and (D) = 0.5 mm keeping the length, width of patch, inset feed line length and width unchanged as compared to the conventional design. In design 1, the inset gap in terms of width (Y) is increased to 0.4mm and in design 2, the inset gap in terms of width (Z) is decreased to 0.1mm as compared to the calculated inset gap in terms of width ($X = 0.2\text{mm}$).

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION :

The plot of RL with resonant frequency (f_r) less than -10 dB of the designed antennas, which operate in 1 GHz to 20 GHz is shown in figure 2. Before and after cut of slits on patch, the fundamental resonant frequency splits into dual frequency bands in 1GHz-20GHz spectrum band. Figure 3 depicts the variations of return loss vs. frequency of a conventional design. In this case, first resonance is seen at $f_{r1} = 5\text{GHz}$, relatively to the specified 5GHz design frequency and so validates the design, as shown

in the diagram. The bandwidths are calculated using the formula [3]. The bandwidth of conventional antenna is about 1 %.

Fig. 2: RL Vs frequency of all three proposed antennas

The antenna resonates at five distinct resonances at $fr_1 = 5$ GHz (having $RL = -18$ dB), $fr_2 = 9$ GHz (having $RL = -17$ dB), $fr_3 = 12.5$ GHz (having $RL = -39$ dB), $fr_4 = 14$ GHz (having $RL = -27$ dB), $fr_5 = 18.8$ GHz (having $RL = -32$ dB) with corresponding impedance bandwidths of $BW_1 = 0.9\%$, $BW_2 = 1.8\%$, $BW_3 = 3.5\%$, $BW_4 = 3.8\%$ for $RL = -29.30$ dB, $BW_5 = 12\%$ respectively for the conventional design as in figure 2. Later, four slits are cut on the patch surface with retaining similar patch dimensions as that of conventional design with increased inset gap of the feed which is as shown in the figure 1.(b). With this configuration, the proposed antenna i.e., design 1, resonates for dual band response with the reduced return loss upto -30 dB at $fr_1 = 4.5$ GHz having bandwidth 1.5% and $fr_2 = 10.5$ GHz with return loss upto -26 dB having bandwidth of 2.2% .

Fig. 3: Surface Current View (SCV) at 5GHz. a) Conventional design, b) Design 1, and c) Design 2

The design 2 shows the patch with four slits which are cut on the patch surface but now the width of the inset gap of the feed is decreased by retaining similar patch dimensions as that of conventional design which is as shown in the figure 1.(c). With this configuration, the proposed antenna i.e., design 2, resonates for dual band response with the reduced return loss up to -23 dB at $f_{r1} = 4.5$ GHz having bandwidth 1.5% and $f_{r2} = 12.5$ GHz with return loss up to -17 dB having bandwidth of 14%. The proposed antenna i.e., design 2 has achieved the maximum bandwidth of 14% suitable for wireless applications.

The Surface Current View (SCV) designs for conventional design, design 1, design 2 are shown in Figure 3. The surface currents are found to be more near the feed and along the patch-width as shown in figure 3(a). The surface currents slightly diminish near the feed with as the inset gap between the feed is increased but notably the currents also get excited on the portion of slits which are cut along the width of patch surface as shown in fig.3(b). The surface currents get more accumulated when the inset feed width gap is decreased to a minimum value ($wf=0.1$ mm) and also along the slits cut on the width of patch surface making it a wide bandwidth antenna resonating at low frequency useful for wireless applications.

Fig. 4: 2D and 3D radiation patterns at 5GHz. a) Conventional design, b) Design 1, and c) Design 2

It is quite clear that, the all the three radiation plots as depicted in 2D and 3D nature at their respective resonance are nearly broadsided in nature with less cross polar levels for the proposed design as shown in figure 4. Figure 5 shows the plots of SWR which are less than 1.5 at respective resonant frequencies of all the three designs of the antenna which signifies less reflected power back to the antenna and also

it is quite clear that the resonant frequency point which confirms a better match of input and load properties.

Fig. 5: SWR curve. a) Conventional design, b) Design 1, and c) Design 2

5. CONCLUSION :

The dual band characteristics of the slit-based patch antennas are proposed in this study. The design 1 has dual resonances at $f_{r1} = 4.5$ GHz (RL= -30 dB) having bandwidth of 1.5 % and $f_{r2} = 10.5$ GHz (RL= -26 dB) having bandwidth of 2.2 % and the design 2 includes two resonances at lower and higher frequency bands, with reduced return loss up to -23 dB at $f_{r1} = 4.5$ GHz and bandwidth of 1.5 %, and return loss up to -17 dB at $f_{r2} = 12.5$ GHz and bandwidth of 14 % for VSWR less than 1.5.

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Simulation Study of Patch Antenna Characteristics loaded with Multislots on Low Cost Dielectric Material

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Abstract— Studies of multislot patch antennas excited by the stripline feeding method has been designed and simulated using IE3D simulation software. A wide dual band characteristic is achieved with better reflection coefficient (RL) at a maximum gain of 5.9 dBi. The impedance bandwidth of the proposed antenna increased from 3% (for a simple patch antenna) to 37.3% by loading different slots on the planer patch. The proposed antenna will find its application in satellite-based applications, radar, wireless applications such as WiFi. The return loss (S_{11}) graph, radiation diagram, current distribution, gain and directivity are given in this paper.

Keywords— Stripline gain, WiFi, frequency, directivity.

Chapter 5

Conclusion & futuristic scope

Chapter 5

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The study in this work reported with the designs and simulation of microstrip patch antenna suitable for 5G applications. The antennas have shown better performance in its parameters such as bandwidth, return loss, radiation properties and VSWR. The antennas are designed for 5G frequency and the simulated resonances are slight near actual band of resonance. This slight variation is due to the simulations constraints or limitations in the EM software.

The futuristic work can also be extended further in the following arenas such as,

- Use of PTFE substrates
- Use of Nano compound materials to get further enhancement in results
- Use of multilayered configurations or substrates
- Use of thick dielectric substrate to get bandwidth enhancement
- Use of novel structure and Metamaterials with respect patch surface
- Use of active and passive elements for getting the reconfigurability

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